

**ADMINISTRATIVE PROBLEMS THAT AFFECT STAFF PERFORMANCE IN
DEP-ED SCHOOLS COVERED BY DAVAO DEL SUR AND DAVAO OCCIDENTAL
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ABSTRACT

The study focused on determining the factors that hinders the performance of an administrative staff in Dep Ed Schools and Division offices especially Administrative Assistants, Administrative Officers, and Planning Designates. It concentrated in the problems that usually arises in identifying, complying and computing personnel benefits and other administrative tasks. How these affect the performance of employees and the effects of these factors.

The study was realized with the use of guide questions and key informant interview. The inputs collected in the interviews were organized according to similarity in nature and the researchers found out that negligence, job description alignment, backlog transactions, no proper endorsement of tasks, insufficiency of budget and supplies, location of work station, unhealthy relationships and unpleasant working environment are the factors that affect the performance of administrative employees in fulfilling their jobs

Keywords:

Administrative problems, staff performance, qualitative study, case study, Department of Education, Davao del Sur, Davao Occidental

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education (DepEd) of the Philippines is an organization that focuses on the welfare of Filipino Learners. It plans programs, policies, and projects that fits best in the needs of a young Filipino. It articulates ideas on how to improve the system of delivering quality services to the students. It gives assistance to challenges faced by the learners especially that the learning system is adapting to Global innovations. The assistance of the Department of Education does not only limit to formal education but also to non-formal education since the Philippines is a developing country that has a majority of learners that are financially unstable. It overlooks the Primary and Secondary Education as well as Alternative Learning system in both public and private and according to the department of the education mandate which is to provide for the establishment and maintenance of a complete, adequate, and integrated system of basic education relevant to the goals of national development.

Every organization especially the government related offices in the Philippines faces a number of adversaries that makes it hard to attain its goals. Nevertheless the Philippine Government has continued to formulate solutions to those inconveniences. Most of the government problems arises in the core of an organization and that is the administrative department to where transaction starts. In the government, public administration plays a big role in managing the public office. According to Public Administration.net (2014) it entails servants implementing a specified policy within the confines of a government executive framework and mostly these executive framework doesn't work in every public office because each organization is composed of leaders and servants that has different personality mix and with that, each government office has its own complexity that possibly doesn't work well with government executive framework thus some problems occur.

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OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the study is to diagnose the administrative problems that hinder administrative staff in performing the task of identifying, complying, and computing the personnel benefits of an employee as well as on other administrative tasks that are related to the job description of an administrative staff. It further identified the situations or problems that can arise in the process of identifying, complying and computing personnel benefits as well as the glitches that can arise in performing other administrative tasks that are included in the list of duties of an administrative staff.

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research method was used in this study. This method was deemed useful in determining the factors that hinders the performance of an administrative staff in identifying, complying, and computing personnel benefits and other transactions that is included in the job functions of an administrative staff in the School and Division level. The participants of the study were administrative Assistants, Administrative Officer, Planning designates, and Division section head of the Division of Davao del Sur and Division of Davao Occidental. The researcher made guide questions concerning transactions and situations that are happening in the daily working hours of an administrative staff and conducted a sit-down interview with employees involved with this type of work to gather significant data for this study. For the interpretation of data, the researcher transcribed the interviews into text documents so the researcher can have a solid backup of findings. The transcribed documents were organized according to similar answers given by the interviewees and findings were extracted easily because they are grouped according to their similarities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The terms stated below are the common administrative problems that affect the performance of an administrative staff in identifying, complying, and computing personnel benefits and other administrative transactions. These terms often makes the transactions difficult to accomplish.

Non-Compliance. Respondents stated that it is difficult to gather important requirements in a transaction because the concerned individuals cannot provide ample data to complete the computation especially differential and step increments. It also happens in the submission of DTRs and oftentimes the division office has resorted to sending a memo to the schools or individuals who causes the delay of submission for them to comply as soon as possible. It can also be inferred in the interviews that another reason for non compliance in the protocols and deadlines is lack of personal knowledge.

In an article entitled “Level of Knowledge and Reasons for Compliance and Non Compliance of City Ordinance No. 8975 among the Urban Barangay Chairmen of Cagayan de Oro City”, it was stated that “the major reason for compliance was personal knowledge while non compliance was institutional illegitimacy and ineffectiveness.” so it is either the employees are not willing to conform with the institutional rules or it is a fault of the institution for not having an effective system of disseminating information and orientation of rules and regulations.

Negligence and Improper Data Management. Transactions are affected oftentimes when papers are misplaced in the office especially that in a day there are a lot of documents that are coming in and out of the division office. These misplaced documents take time to be retrieved and it is one of the cause of delay on important transactions such as computation of differentials, step increments, hardship allowances and other personnel benefits. Having a lot of paper documents in the office consumes a lot of space and causes instances that leads to time consuming processes of retrieving what was lost.

In an Efficiency case study of Grand Casinos concerning human resource problems in processing paperwork, a similar situation of having problems in Negligence and Proper Data Management has been experienced. It has been identified that in an office, negligence and non compliance in proper data management causes delays in transactions. There were occurrence of contracts that are not approved on time, duplication of documents, and increased spending of penalty charges, because there is lack of proper data management and papers going in and out on a certain department are neglected due to pending transactions that are piled up and became idle for quite sometime.

Job description mismatch. In government service job description, there is an intriguing phrase of “Other related services” stated as one of the tasks of an employee and oftentimes the said “related services” goes beyond its nature of being “related” because some of the tasks are not in line with office works anymore. A respondent stated that he was tasked to cook by the teacher and sometimes they ask him to do personal tasks that are not related to his work. Sometimes the Other related services adds up to the piles of pending workload resulting to the delay of the progress in accomplishing the task related to the job description of the employee.

Job description as said in the article “ The Effect of Job Descriptions on Employee Performance” enhance the employee’s efficiency in the workplace. It is stated in the article that there are some cases where Job description is not present and it led to unbalanced division of workload in the workplace because employees tend to do tasks that are not meant for them to accomplish and there are people who are underloaded and overloaded with jobs. A job description is a vital tool in knowing the responsibilities of an employee and it also shows the ranking of significance of each task that a member of an organization has to do. It prevents misunderstanding of what work is to be done and it reduces the risk of having pending works because the employee has done what he is tasked for it is clearly stated in his Job description. Furthermore it is also said that having Job mismatch is not entirely negative in nature because there are some instances where it prevents employees from thinking that one work is not their responsibility. Sometimes it reduces the instance of idle works because an employee assumes that a certain duty is his/hers so it performs the tasks required for that work even if it is a task of another employee. It is also an avenue of enhancing flexibility of employees to perform their peers’ responsibilities and it enhances teamwork between staffs of an organization.

Backlog Transactions. Administrative tasks in a school setting are performed by the designated planning officers of the schools which are originally teachers but since there are schools that do not have administrative assistant personnel assigned to them, they are given ancillary tasks to fill the role of the administrative assistant. With them being a teacher and an administrative assistant at the same time, it wouldn’t be a wonder why there are tasks and functions that are not timely accomplished and it results to backlog transactions. The piled up transactions delays the accomplishment of tasks and goals of an organization.

A backlog is a collection of tasks that are not yet completed. In financial aspect Backlog transactions refers to the company’s pending orders waiting to be responded or a pile of Financial papers that needs to be dealt with. Backlog transactions can be in public and private organizations. In a public company setting backlog transactions has an implication that something is wrong in a company’s performance in meeting the end-user’s demands thus when there are backlog transactions delays in performing the task efficiently happens

A perfect example of a backlog is when Apple released the iPhone X, the 10th anniversary edition of the iPhone brand in October 2017. There was an overwhelming initial demand for the mobile device and it created a backlog on pre-orders. Apple has not other options but to delay the shipments to late November and then again to December for the pre-orders that was made upon the launching. A lot of people perceived and commented that the backlog is an indication of poor sales forecasting of Apple because a similar situation happened in 2015 when the company debuted the Apple Watch which is another innovation product of Apple.

No proper endorsement of tasks. When one is promoted or in some cases resigned or retires in an organization, it is a protocol to train the employee who would take over the job that was left, and sometimes due to reasons like urgency, lack of concern, selfishness and the likes, succeeding employees finds it hard to adjust and learn the basics of the job given. It results to the delay of transactions due to lack of knowledge on the job at hand, mistakes that are often incurred in accomplishing the task, and it is time consuming to learn and perform tasks at the same time.

In an article entitled “7 Guidelines for Delegating tasks to Employees” it was said that not everything can be delegated. Having a certain position in an organization can be likened to having a unique role in a certain setting especially that by gaining that position, it means that a certain individual has achieved the right amount of experience and skills to perform the work productively. A certain job position has some tasks and projects that needs to be done only by the person having a certain position. But there are also tasks that someone else in the company can handle. It is said that “Part of being an effective delegator is being able to determine which types of tasks are suitable for delegation and which types are not”. In some cases, it is difficult to endorse tasks to a co-worker because the one in position feels like none of the tasks that he has to do can be delegated to another but eventually it will be okay to delegate and share tasks for a faster accomplishment. Proper breakdown of tasks based on their skill requirement is a key on an effective task endorsement. The tasks that has fewer skill

requirement and complexity can be delegated so someone else in the company can do it in case that the person in position is away or if that person has retired or resigned in the agency.

Money and insufficient supplies. The government always opts to the “Lowest responsive bidder” when it comes to purchasing of materials and supplies of the different public agencies and so, the availability of supplies depends on the sufficiency of funds and its procurement. In the school setting, most administrative assistants and planning officers has the struggle of having adequate supplies especially bond papers and computer inks who are the primary supplies in processing of documents. It results to instances where these employees use their own money to purchase materials to be used in school and It has become a problem to these employees because it prevents a speedy transaction and compliance to reports especially that salaries of these employees are only given once a month and transactions and deadlines are to be met timely.

As said in a case study entitled “Procurement Process at the Department of Education Philippines, Division of Cagayan de Oro City: Looking beyond the legal framework”; “A Public Procurement reform Act was enacted to ensure that there is transparency, competitiveness, streamlined procurement process, and civil monitoring in the procurement process” but in reality because of these objectives, acquiring supplies became a very critical and long process to deal with and mostly the administrative staffs and other employees resort into using their own money just to buy supplies to accomplish their task.

Location of Work Station. Respondents say that the location of station is a factor on the delay of transactions because of the fortuitous events that can occur while the employee is on its way to submit the papers in the division or in delivering supplies and equipment to the station. An administrative assistant stated that transporting their supplies in the station is such a hassle because sometimes there are no vehicles available to deliver the items. Weather conditions in the station adds up to the delay of transactions because some stations are located in the outskirts and when it rains, flooding and landslides affects the speedy delivery of transactions.

Unhealthy relationships and unpleasant working environment. Conflict is a factor in the delay of transactions because the clashing of opinions creates a misunderstanding and miscommunication in the office. When this happens, many transactions are affected due to the trust issues and selfishness of the members on the organization. This results to the delay of transactions in a sense that mistakes in the processing and complying of documents happens continuously because of lack in good communication within the office and whenever there are mistakes, transactions are repeated again and it causes a delay.

CONCLUSION

Every organization has its own unique situation that creates a factor that can affect the identification, compilation, computation and other administrative transactions in the office. Each organization has its own way of solving differences as well as adapting to the culture of the organization. The system in one organization might work in itself but it can be ineffective in another. Awareness and initiative in performing tasks that are not stated in the Job description makes transactions speedy in a sense that the concern of an employee in attaining organizational goals plays a huge role in accomplishing difficult tasks. Adaptability makes a good difference in completing a transaction and good communication makes goals more attainable.

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